

Impact of Internal Marketing on Internal Customer Satisfaction and Task Performance. Evidence from Automobile Companies in Hyderabad Pakistan

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Abstract: *The purpose of the study is to find out the impact of internal marketing on job satisfaction, internal customer satisfaction and task performance among the automobile companies in Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan. Internal marketing refers to the way employees are considered as internal customers and is achieved by internal communication, empowerment, training and recognition, and with the goal of increasing employee satisfaction and organizational performance. The study covers an important research gap, as little empirical evidence has been found on internal marketing in the automobile sector and manufacturing sector in Pakistan. The approach used was quantitative research and the design was cross sectional survey. Two hundred and eighty-seven employees from major automobile industries such as Toyota, Suzuki, Honda, Changan, Hyundai and MG were selected to collect data. Stratified random sampling was used to collect data from the employees of all organizations. Data collected were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS- SEM) with software SmartPLS. The results indicated that the internal marketing has a notable positive relationship with job satisfaction, internal customer satisfaction and task performance. Furthermore, the effect of internal marketing on internal customer satisfaction as well as task performance is mediated by job satisfaction to a great extent. Reliability and validity tests were used to verify and confirm all constructs were statistically strong and acceptable for analysis. The research indicates that the internal marketing process has a positive effect on employees' satisfaction and organization performance in the automobile industry. The study offers managers and human resource practitioners' useful insights for supporting employee-centric approaches to increase the organization's performance and success in the long-term.*

Keywords: Internal Marketing (IM), Internal Customer Satisfaction (ICS), Task Performance (TP), Job Satisfaction (JS), Automobile Companies (AC)

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

Satisfaction and retention of potential customers is one of the most important components of every organization and their efforts directly lead towards the success of the organization. Issue arises when organizations bear high cost for the potential employees in automobile or service industries. Most of the industries suffer due to less retention of talented employees and they also suffer from training expenses point of view, this also influences employee job satisfaction (Brown and Mitchell, 1993).

One of the studies (Jeon and Choi 2012) shows satisfaction of employees leads to satisfaction of customers. This is the reason that to satisfy customers, employees must be satisfied. The concept of internal marketing started in the year 19s as an initiative to develop high quality HR services (Akbari et al., 2019). Internal marketing is considered as a set of human resource practices and policies where employees are considered and treated as an internal customer (Asiedu et al., 2014). Internal Marketing is believed to be useful in the management of the human resource from a marketing point of view (Huang, 2020). Based on this, employees can be considered as the internal customers of an organization (Chuang et al., 2015). Internal marketing covers both employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction (Rafiq & Ahmed, 2000). Based on this customer satisfaction achieved through attraction, motivation of high-quality human resource. Internal Marketing practices incorporate empowerment that gives responsibility to employees for the quality services. Employees feel satisfied with this authority and perform better in their jobs. By assigning authority, they become more responsible to get their organizational objective. Results show that employees ' participation in decision making improves not only their loyalty but also their job satisfaction (Kim, 2002). Employees actively participation in decision making, become a part of overall organization and align with organizational objectives.

1.1 Problem Statement

In today's competitive business environment, automobile companies depend on the performance and customer satisfaction to balance service quality and operational efficiency. However, many organizations including those in the automobile companies of Hyderabad, most of time look after the importance of internal marketing practices that treat employees as internal customers. Lack of effective internal marketing such as poor communication, unproductive employee training, lack of recognition and poor support from management can lead to low job satisfaction, reduced internal customer satisfaction will lead to poor task performance.

Significance of the Study

This research carries significant importance from academic and practical sides within the automobile industry of Hyderabad Pakistan. Through examining the impact of internal marketing on internal customer satisfaction and task performance. Study contributes in detail understanding of how internal organizational practices influence employee attitudes and performance outcomes. From a management point of view, the results will help out HR managers and executives in developing better and better internal marketing strategies that strengthen employee satisfaction, motivation to increase overall productivity. Such initiatives of internal marketing such as communication, empowerment, recognition and training affect employee satisfaction can help organizations improve task performance and deliver superior results to external customers.

1.2 Research Objectives

RO1: To determine the impact of internal marketing on job satisfaction.

RO2: To find the impact of internal marketing on internal customer satisfaction.

RO3: To investigate the impact of internal marketing on task performance.

RO4: To determine the mediating effect of job satisfaction between internal marketing and internal customer satisfaction.

RO5: To examine the mediating effect of job satisfaction between internal marketing and task performance.

2.0 Literature Review

Internal Marketing (IM) is a strategic instrument where the organizations view employees as internal customers, promote employee satisfaction, as well as integrate the workforce behavior with the organizational

goals. IM links HR activities with performance in operations, which is a significant issue in competitive markets like Pakistan.

The last empirical study of Pakistan is carried out in the commercial banking industry of Sindh (2025) in which it was established that internal communication, professional development opportunities as well as empowerment practices are important in enhancing job satisfaction. On the same note, Ahmed and Imran (2023) analyzed the internal marketing within the higher education sector and found that IM practices have a great effect on job satisfaction by employees. Before that, Amin et al. (2022) researched the IM within the telecommunication sector in Pakistan.

Even though they did not concentrate on the job satisfaction, their results affirmed that IM practices improve the outcomes of engagement and sustainability, which supports the applicability of IM in service and manufacturing based settings. These mechanisms are also supported by international evidence. The study by Nemteanu and Dabija (2021) has shown that the impact of internal marketing on employee satisfaction and performance outcomes are significant and correspond to all the processes discussed in the theoretical framework of SET and AMO. Furthermore, the researchers Qionlei Yu et al. (2019) found that internal market orientation is beneficial to firm performance because it boosts employee organisational commitment and retention, which underscores the need for internal communication and interdepartmental relationships.

A study by Amir Ishaque and Khurram Shahzad (2016) revealed that internal marketing had a positive effect on the job satisfaction of employees, job performance and job citizenship of the employees and that job satisfaction was a partial mediator in the relationship between internal marketing, job performance and job citizenship. Previous studies in Pakistan like Ali et al. (2014) in the Sialkot manufacturing industry have focused on the importance of IM in employee retention. Even though the research was not focused on directly testing internal customer satisfaction or even task performance, it showed the relevance of IM to the manufacturing settings and the necessity of further research in this field. IM is theoretically based even further. An international research by Ebru Aykan and Ebru Sönmez (2014) studied the relationship between internal marketing practices and task and contextual performances of employees, and found that perceived organizational justice was in the middle of the relationship. Lings (2004) broadened the idea by suggesting that employees should also be treated as internal customers whose satisfaction is determined by way of communication, training and support to the organization similar to external customers. Ahmed and Rafiq (1995) described IM as a combination of goal-based initiatives directed towards educating, motivating and communicating with employees in order to internalize the organizational goals. In the past, Locke (1976) already conceptualized job satisfaction as a positive state of emotion following job experiences, which determine

performance, service behavior and employee retention.

In conclusion, the literature shows that there is a high degree of support on the relationships between IM and job satisfaction, job satisfaction and performance and the overall role that IM plays in both results.

Nevertheless, the majority of the Pakistani research has been on service industry, including banks, higher education, and telecommunication. There is limited evidence connecting IM and internal customer satisfaction and task performance especially via job satisfaction to the Pakistani automobile or manufacturing industries. Therefore, this research fills this gap as it uses these relations to the automobile industry in Hyderabad, Sindh, where empirical testing is still not abundant.

3.0 Research Methodology

The study is based on a quantitative study designed to examine the relationships between internal marketing, job satisfaction, internal customer satisfaction and task performance in the automobile industry in Hyderabad, Pakistan. Quantitative approach makes it possible to verify hypotheses and discover causal relationships based on measurable data, which ensures objectivity, consistency and statistical validity based on numerical analysis. In this research, the primary objective is explanatory and is focused on the role that internal marketing strategies play in influencing the internal customer satisfaction and task performance both directly and indirectly through job satisfaction. This study is based on the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) (Deci and Ryan, 2000) which comes up with the idea that internal marketing practices can meet the intrinsic psychological needs of the employees such as autonomy, competence and relatedness which subsequently lead to job satisfaction and job performance. Additionally, The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Demerouti et al., 2001) explains how internal marketing acts as an organizational resource leading to a lower job strain and a greater engagement that results in greater satisfaction and improved output of the tasks. Through these relationships, the study aims at providing empirical evidence on the ability of internal marketing in terms of improving employee-related outcomes and overall organizational performance in the automobile industry in Pakistan.

The research will be based on a descriptive and causal paradigm that is suitable in the identification of patterns and cause and effect relationships of the variables being studied. There is a cross-sectional survey methodology, where the data were collected at one point in time and on the sample of people who work in automobile companies. Through this method, it is possible to have a holistic understanding of the variables and their relationships with each other without manipulating external elements. The study relies on the primary data collected by directly undertaking interviews with the employees in the automobile industry of Hyderabad, Sindh, through a structured survey questionnaire. This method will ensure the authenticity, reliability and consistency of the information that is gathered and the suitability of such information to the research objectives.

The sample size comprises workers of six major automobile companies namely Toyota, Suzuki, Honda, Changan, Hyundai and MG which are located in Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan, where the number of individuals who are employed by these companies are more than 800 professionals working in different divisions and

hierarchy levels. This population is considered suitable in studying the impacts of internal marketing strategies on employee satisfaction and employee performance. A probability sampling technique, namely, stratified random sampling is used to ensure representativeness and minimize bias. Through this method the population is divided into similar subgroups with the help of relevant attributes like department or rank, and random samples are taken out of each subgroup so that all the subgroups are represented fairly. This type of sampling will help increase the precision of the estimates and reduce error of sampling since all employees will have an equal opportunity to participate.

To achieve the most accurate results, the research should employ the largest sample possible to make it more representative since larger the sample size, the more of a picture of credibility it will have. Since the limitations are high, such as the budget, time, access to participants, etc and there is no possibility to gather data from the whole population, a small section of the population was selected to form a sample (LoBiondo-Wood and Haber, 1998). To

determine the sample size of our research, we have taken the procedure of average sample size as stated on base papers. The sample size in one of the studies is 400 (Babalola et al., 2023), in the second research paper it is 250 (Waheed et al., 2025) and in the third research article it is 150 (Shabbir and Salaria, 2014).

$$N = (400 + 250 + 150) / 3 = 267$$

Accordingly, we will also be using the sample of 267 respondents to calculate our results. The sample size used is adequate in undertaking advanced statistical procedures and testing of hypotheses using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The study considers four main variables, including internal marketing as the independent variable, job satisfaction as the mediating variable, internal customer satisfaction and task performance as the dependent variables. Validated scales of previous studies are used to assess each construct; this will help to provide content validity and reliability.

The structured questionnaire is the main research instrument, and it has two sections. The first section collects the demographic information (age, gender, level of education, income level, marital status and the name of the organization). Questions on the second part are intended to measure internal marketing, job satisfaction, internal customer satisfaction and task performance. All the items will be rated by the respondents on a five- point Likert scale. The scale is given as follows:

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly Agree

S. No.	Variables	No of items	Scale	Source
1	Internal Marketing	5	Five-point Likert scale	Berry & Parasuraman (1991)
2	Internal Customer Satisfaction	5	Five-point Likert scale	Homburg et al. (2005)
3	Task Performance	5	Five-point Likert scale	Williams and Anderson (1991)
4	Job Satisfaction	5	Five-point Likert scale	Spector (1985)

Table 1: Layout of Questionnaire.

The collected data was analyzed with the help of SmartPLS. SmartPLS software designed on the basis of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). This is the technique that is applicable for the analysis of complex models with many dependent variables and mediating effects. Analyzing will involve the descriptive statistics to give a summary of demographic data and structural model analysis to test the proposed relationships between the variables. The SmartPLS will help to estimate the direct and indirect effects correctly to provide an in-depth insight into the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between internal marketing and employee performance results.

3.6 Conceptual Framework

4.0 Data Analysis and Findings

Demographic Frequency

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	224	78.0	78.0	78.0
	Female	63	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	287	100.0	100.0	
Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	18 - 25	44	15.3	15.3	15.3

Valid	26 - 35	180	62.7	62.7	78.0
	36 - 45	59	20.6	20.6	98.6
	46 - 55	4	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	287	100.0	100.0	

Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Graduate	208	72.5	72.5	72.5
	Post Graduate	39	13.6	13.6	86.1
	Other	40	13.9	13.9	100.0
	Total	287	100.0	100.0	

Employment Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Full Time	215	74.9	74.9	74.9
	Part Time	19	6.6	6.6	81.5
	Other	53	18.5	18.5	100.0
	Total	287	100.0	100.0	

Organizations you are employed

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Toyota	99	34.5	34.5	34.5
	Suzuki	31	10.8	10.8	45.3
	Changan	36	12.5	12.5	57.8
	Honda	43	15.0	15.0	72.8

Valid	Hyundai	32	11.1	11.1	84.0
	MG	26	9.1	9.1	93.0
	Other	20	7.0	7.0	100.0
	Total	287	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Demographics of Respondents

Above findings show the demographics of respondents through gender, age qualification, employment status and in last organizations in which they are employed. A total of 287 responses including employees that are working in automobile industries and dealers from Hyderabad Sindh have attempted to fill out questionnaires.

4.1.1 Gender

Among the gender, 224 participants were male with percent of (78.0%), after that 63 participants were females comprising the percent of (22.0%) from the overall total participants.

4.1.2 Age

Regarding the age groups, most of the participants were from the age range of 26 to 35 age group, total participants in this age group were 180 with percent of (62.7%), in this age group most of the employees were from middle level. The second highest age group was 35 to 45 responses with a percentage of (20.6%), in this age group most of the respondents were managers and executive level employees of automobile industries. After that 44 participants were in the age range of 18 to 25 comprising percent of (15.3%), in this range most of the internees fall in this age group. 4 employees were from the age group of 46 to 55 emphasizing percent of (1.4%), these employees were senior executive level employees of automobile industries.

4.1.3 Employment Status

Responses with employment status shown by the employees in 3 categories, full time employees, part time employees and others. Highest respondents were full time employees with 215 having (74.9%). Then we have part time employees 19 responses with (6.6%). In last there were options of other which includes students with interns are in number of 53 with (18%).

4.1.4 Qualification

Participants in the qualification demographic most fell in the graduate category around 208 with percent of (72.5%). In the post graduate there were 39 respondents with percent of (13.6%). In last there was option of other in which

4.1.5 Organizations employees working

Considering the participants working in the different automobile industries and also including the dealers as well. 6 different companies we have selected and collected responses from their employees, most of the employees were from Toyota with 99 responses containing a percentage of (34.9%). Then another company

Honda in which 43 employees participated having (15.0%) percentage. 36 responses collected from Changan comprising a percentage of (12.5%). Responses collected from Hyundai were 32 with the percent of (11.1%). 31 employees responded from Suzuki emphasizing (10.8%). 26 participants were from MG (9.1%). Last option of this demographic was others in which 20 responses collected with percent of (7.0%), these were few employees working in other automobile industries excluding all above companies.

4.2 Reliability and Validity Analysis

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Internal Customer Satisfaction	0.924	0.910	0.943	0.768
Internal Marketing	0.914	0.916	0.935	0.743
Job Satisfaction	0.938	0.920	0.953	0.802
Task Performance	0.930	0.932	0.947	0.782

Table 3: Reliability and Validity

Table 3 elaborates the results of reliability and validity for the four variables, one out of the is independent variable represented as Internal Marketing (IM), then there are two dependent variables shows as Internal Customer Satisfaction (ICS) and Task Performance (TP), one of them is mediator known as Job Satisfaction

(JS) analyzed in this study. Every construct shows high reliability and convergent validity, as shown by Cronbach's Alpha, rho_a, Composite Reliability rho_c and Average Variance Extraction (AVE).

Cronbach's Alpha values for Internal Customer Satisfaction and Job Satisfaction vary between 0.924 and 0.938, showing a strong degree of internal consistency. Job Satisfaction shows the highest Alpha value of 0.938, indicating very reliable item responses, whereas Internal Marketing has the somewhat low Alpha at 0.914 as compared to others but it has crossed the suggested margin of 0.70 efficiently.

Furthermore rho_A results additionally verify the dependability, falling between 0.910 and 0.920. Task Performance exhibits the highest reliability (rho_A = 0.932), Internal Customer Satisfaction shows a slightly low value of rho_A = 0.910, and remains within an acceptable margin of reliability range. Internal Marketing (0.916) and Job Satisfaction (0.920) also exhibit strong rho_A values, showing the proof of internal stability.

Composite Reliability rho_c values range from 0.943 to 0.953, reflecting excellent measurement quality across all constructs. Average Variation Extraction AVE values (0.768 to 0.802) shows enough convergent validity, as each construct explains over 76.8% of the variance was shown in its indicators. Job Satisfaction once more demonstrates the greatest convergent validity (AVE = 0.802), whereas Internal Marketing showing the low value yet still in acceptable margin AVE at 0.550.

Concluding, findings regarding reliability and validity indicate that all constructs are strong and suitable for subsequent structural model analysis.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

4.3 Discriminant Validity

4.3.1 HTMT Matrix

Discriminant validity was determined by using the HTMT criterion, and the results shows that all constructs were empirically separate. The HTMT values for ICS ranged from 0.850 to 0.969 with those for IM ranging from 0.957 to 0.892. Although the value between IM and JS (0.892) was close to the upper limit usually accepted in social science research it was still within an acceptable range. The relationships between TP ranged from 0.850 to 0.848. Values for some did not fall below 0.90 (or 0.85 in more conservative terms) suggesting somewhat acceptable discriminant validity.

	ICS	IM	JS	TP
ICS				
IM	0.957			
JS	0.969	0.892		
TP	0.850	0.848	0.797	

Table 4: HTMT Matrix

4.3.2 Fornell Larker Criterion

Fornell–Larcker analysis further illustrates discriminant validity. The square root of the AVE for each construct surpassed its correlations with other constructs in all instances. ICS exhibited a value of 0.876, IM 0.862, JS 0.896, and TP 0.885 along the diagonal, each exceeding the inter construct correlations. These results show that each construct accounted for more variance from its own indicators than from other constructs, thus confirming the distinct nature of the key variables in the study.

	Internal Customer Satisfaction	Internal Marketing	Job Satisfaction	Task Performance
Internal Customer Satisfaction	0.876			
Internal Marketing	0.882	0.862		
Job Satisfaction	0.904	0.829	0.896	
Task Performance	0.789	0.783	0.746	0.885

Table 5: Fornell Larcker Criterion

4.4 R – Square

The structural model demonstrated strong explanatory power for the primary endogenous variables. ICS

achieved an R² value of 0.873, with an adjusted R² of 0.872, signifying that 87% of the variance in internal customer satisfaction among the employees of automobile companies in the internal marketing was explained by its predictors. Job Satisfaction (JS) showed a value R² value of 0.687, with an adjusted R² of 0.6686 indicating that 68% of its variance was attributed to the associated independent variables. These figures reflect moderate to substantial levels of predictive accuracy, reinforcing the significance of the relationships posited in the model.

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Internal Customer Satisfaction	0.873	0.872
Job Satisfaction	0.687	0.686
Task Performance	0.644	0.641

Table 6: R Square

4.5 Model Fit

Model fit yielded acceptable outcomes for a PLS-SEM model. The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) registered at 0.049 for both the saturated and estimated models, which is slightly above the ideal cut-off of 0.08 but still regarded as adequate given the complexity of the model. Additional indices, including d_{ULS} (0.499), d_G (0.609), and Chi-square (975.055), further characterize the model’s performance, while the (NFI) was 0.847, indicating a moderate fit. This model fit indices corroborate the adequacy of the proposed structural model in capturing the relationships among generational differences, family business climate, job satisfaction, and employee performance.

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.049	0.050
d_{ULS}	0.499	0.527
d_G	0.609	0.615
Chi-square	975.055	982.419
NFI	0.847	0.845

Table 7: Model Fit

4.6 VIF

4.6.1 Outer VIF

All the items in the constructs of Internal Customer Satisfaction (ICS), Internal Marketing (IM), Job Satisfaction (JS), and Task Performance (TP) were found to be within acceptable limits of multicollinearity

through the evaluation at the indicator level using Outer VIF values. The VIF values ranged from 3.800 to 3.937, with ICS items values from 3.800 to 3.616, IM items from 2.296 to 2.810, JS items from 3.952 to 4.406, and TP items from 4.340 to 4.406. The stability of the measurement model was confirmed by the results, as all the values were lower than the threshold value of 5, which indicates that there was no significant multicollinearity among the indicators.

	VIF
ICS1	3.800
ICS2	2.424
ICS3	4.392
ICS4	2.612
ICS5	3.616
IM1	2.296
IM2	3.428
IM3	2.766
IM4	3.246
IM5	2.810
JS1	3.952
JS2	3.668
JS3	5.148
JS4	3.644
JS5	4.406
TP1	4.340
TP2	3.506
TP3	4.272
TP4	3.364
TP5	3.937

Table 8: Outer VIF

4.6.2 Inner VIF

The values of inner VIFs that were investigated to check collinearity among the predictor constructs of the structural model. No multicollinearity exists in this model since all the values of VOF are below the value in the margin 3,193 and the value of 3.3 is the limit for the multicollinearity. From this structural model also don't have collinearity problem and can be built up hypothesis test structures.

	Internal Customer Satisfaction	Internal Marketing	Job Satisfaction	Task Performance
Internal Customer Satisfaction				

Internal Marketing	3.193		1.000	3.193
Job Satisfaction	3.193			3.193
Task Performance				

4.7 Hypothesis Testing and Discussion

The hypothesis is accepted because the p-value is less than the 0.05 significance level for H1: Internal marketing has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction. The path coefficient ($\beta = 0.829$) is positive, the t-value (29.464) is above 1.96 and the p value (0.000) is lower than 0.05 which indicates that the path coefficient is of significant effect.

Results accepted the hypothesis for H2, which suggests a positive and significant relationship between Internal Marketing to Internal Customer Satisfaction. The path coefficient is positive ($\beta = 0.426$) which suggests the anticipated direction of the relationship, and the t-value (6.827) is greater than 1.96 and the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05 which shows a positive significance at the 95% level of confidence.

The hypothesis is also accepted for H3 which relates to the positive and significant effect of Internal Marketing on Take Performance. The path coefficient is positive ($\beta = 0.526$), the t value (5.576) is greater than the required value, and the p value is (0.000) which is less than the required value (0.05). This means that with good internal marketing it is possible to improve the performance of job tasks considerably.

The hypothesis H4, which proposes that Job Satisfaction is a mediator between the Internal Marketing and Internal Customer Satisfaction, is accepted. There is a strong mediation effect of IM to JS to ICS. The direct path from IM to JS is positive and significant ($\beta = 0.829, p = 0.000$) which means the computed indirect effect is negligible ($\beta_{\text{indirect}} \approx -0.829 \times 0.000 = 0.000$). This indirect effect is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) as shown by bootstrapped mediation analysis, which means that job satisfaction has the effect of Internal Marketing and Internal Customer Satisfaction. That is, internal marketing characteristics do contribute to improved internal customer satisfaction in the form of an increase in job satisfaction.

H5 is accepted for H5: Internal Marketing \rightarrow Job Satisfaction \rightarrow Task Performance and the mediation is partial. However, the indirect effect through the two important paths (IM \rightarrow JS \rightarrow TP) is large ($\beta_{\text{indirect}} = 0.829 \times 0.002 = 0.016$). An indirect effect is statistically significant using bootstrapped analysis ($p < 0.05$). The direct path from Internal Marketing to Task Performance is still significant ($\beta = 0.526, p = 0.000$) and thus the pattern is interpreted as full mediation, that is, Internal Marketing has a significant direct pathway and also a significant indirect pathway through the increased job satisfaction.

	Original sample or Beta	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Remarks
IM -> ICS	0.426	6.827	0.000	Accepted
IM -> JS	0.829	29.464	0.000	Accepted
IM -> TP	0.526	5.576	0.000	Accepted
JS -> ICS	0.550	9.257	0.000	Accepted
JS -> TP	0.310	3.161	0.002	Accepted

Table 10: Hypothesis Testing**Conclusion**

In this study, the impact of internal marketing on job satisfaction, internal customer satisfaction and task performance of employees in automobile companies of Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan was investigated. The results confirmed that internal marketing has an important contribution to enhance the outcomes of the employees in the automobile sector. The findings showed that internal marketing had a significant role in increasing the employees' job satisfaction. Companies can foster a positive workplace culture by offering good communication, empowering employees, offering rewards and providing training. Companies that implement the right communication, employee empowerment, rewards and training create a better working environment, which motivates employees to feel satisfied with their job. Also, internal marketing was positively related with internal customer satisfaction, indicating that employees react positively to internal marketing of an organization as internal customers. The study also showed that internal marketing positively contributes to the performance of the tasks. Those who feel they are benefiting from positive internal marketing act effectively and help the organization meet its objectives. Furthermore, job satisfaction was identified as a mediating variable between internal marketing and internal customer satisfaction as well as task performance, therefore, the need for employee satisfaction as a way of strengthening organizational performance was given attention.

In conclusion, the study indicates that internal marketing is a valuable organizational strategy as it has the potential to create high employee attitudes and performance results in the automobile industry of Pakistan.

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